

ACCESSIBILITY AND SUSTAINABILITY IN CATALAN PRIMARY SCHOOLS' CURRICULUM: BRIDGING THE GAP

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Abstract

In today's educational landscape, fostering sustainability and inclusivity are imperative goals for preparing students to navigate a complex and interconnected world. In 2021, the Council of the European Union published a resolution outlining a strategic framework for European cooperation in education, emphasizing its essential role in shaping a cohesive, inclusive, digital, sustainable, and resilient society. This framework led to a review of the educational system in Spain, resulting in the approval of Decret 175/2022 in Catalonia, which established a new curriculum for primary education.

Following the goals established by the European Union and UNESCO, the new Catalan primary school curriculum places a strong emphasis on sustainability. This includes fostering a deep awareness and understanding of sustainability and respectful practices towards the environment among students. The curriculum seeks to encourage students to actively seek solutions in response to the pressing challenges posed by the climate crisis. However, it falls short in addressing topics related to accessibility and raising awareness of individuals with different abilities.

This presentation will review the current Catalan curriculum and identify the gaps found in accessibility and sustainability education. It will introduce how accessibility and sustainability principles can be included in the current curriculum through the pilot methodology CROMA-GreenSCENT, developed through a series of workshops designed to train prospective primary school teachers in Catalonia. These workshops equipped trainers with the tools to integrate the principles of sustainability and accessibility using 360° storytelling into their teaching. In doing so, trainers were able to prepare students not only to understand and tackle environmental issues but also to recognise the barriers that can hinder access to important environmental information.

Keywords: Education, sustainability, accessibility, curriculum.

1 INTRODUCTION

In today's educational landscape, fostering sustainability and inclusivity are imperative goals for preparing students to navigate a complex and interconnected world. In 2021, the Council of the European Union published a resolution outlining a strategic framework for European cooperation in education. This resolution highlighted the essential role of education and training in shaping Europe's future, particularly as society, and the strive to become more cohesive, inclusive, digital, sustainable, green, and resilient [1].

This resolution led to the publication of Real Decreto 157/2022 [2] in Spain, which involved revising and adapting the educational system to the challenges and goals of the 21st century, aligning with objectives set by the European Union and UNESCO for the 2020-2030 decade. While this decree established the foundational framework to be followed, each education administration was tasked with establishing the specific curriculum for their respective territory. In Catalonia, this process culminated in the approval of Decret 175/2022 [3], which established the new Catalan curriculum.

This article aims to analyse the incorporation of sustainability and accessibility within the new primary school curriculum while identifying existing gaps. Additionally, we will introduce the CROMA-GreenSCENT workshop and explain how it addresses these gaps to enhance children's learning experiences, fostering inclusivity and sustainability within the educational setting.

2 METHODOLOGY

This study investigates the integration of knowledge regarding sustainability, accessibility, and disability in the new primary school curriculums in Catalonia. The research was conducted in collaboration with the CROMA program, which focuses on primary school students, thereby limiting our analysis to the curriculum for this educational stage.

The implementation of the new Catalan curriculum in primary schools began in the school year 2022-2023 for 1st, 3rd, and 5th year students. Subsequently, it is being rolled out to the remaining primary school years during the 2023-2024 academic year. Schools have been assigned a three-year period to gradually implement all the changes outlined in the new curriculum, ensuring a progressive adaptation to the updated educational standards [4].

The new primary school curriculum is structured into eight knowledge areas [5]:

- Aranese Language and Literature from Val d'Aran, Catalan Language and Literature, and Spanish Language and Literature
- Knowledge of the Natural, Social and Cultural Environment
- Arts Education
- Civic Values and Ethics Education
- Physical Education
- Foreign Language
- Mathematics
- Second Foreign Language

To conduct this analysis, we performed a qualitative content review of the curriculum documents for each knowledge area. Each document was examined for references to knowledge related to sustainability, accessibility and disabilities. Our focus was on identifying if these concepts were integrated within the curriculum, and, if so, how.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Sustainability within the primary school curriculum

The acquisition of knowledge regarding sustainability, climate change, and sustainable practices is a topic very present in the primary curriculum, as a whole, as it is considered in all knowledge areas in varying degrees.

Knowledge of the Natural, Social and Cultural Environment [6] is the area that places the biggest emphasis in these concepts. In 1st and 2nd year, students delve into understanding the environment, including natural landscapes, human-altered areas, and their respective elements. They explore actions geared towards conserving, enhancing, and promoting the sustainability of shared resources. Additionally, they grasp the interconnection between the natural and human water cycles, with an aim to foster sustainable water resource management practices. Furthermore, students learn to recognise and engage in responsible behaviours focused on reducing, reusing, and recycling waste within their immediate surroundings.

In 3rd and 4th year, students are introduced to the causes and effects of climate change, as well as its impact on Earth's landscapes, while also identifying mitigation measures related to human activities. They gain an understanding of how human actions contribute to the transformation and degradation of natural ecosystems, prompting exploration of conservation and protection measures for both present and future generations. Additionally, they develop attitudes of responsible consumption towards natural resources and energy sources across different aspects of life. Furthermore, they are taught to recognise and adopt responsible consumption habits, appreciate the benefits of locally sourced products, and advocate for consumer rights.

Finally, in 5th and 6th year, students are tasked with identifying and analysing the causes and impacts of climate change, while also proposing measures for both mitigation and adaptation. They delve into the examination of ecological footprints across various global regions and explore the finite resources of our planet, investigating the exploitation processes that lead to their depletion. Additionally, they assess actions geared towards achieving sustainable development goals, analysing the repercussions of lifestyle choices. Furthermore, they evaluate the environmental and social responsibilities of companies and cooperatives, while also exploring concepts like green economies, responsible consumption, and the importance of supporting local products.

Sustainability is also present in Civic Values and Ethics Education [7], as one of the focuses of this area is on sustainability and environmental ethics. In this area, students in 5th and 6th year aim to understand

the relationship between human lifestyles and the environment. They identify the major eco-social challenges shaping the global agenda and debate on effective approaches to address them. The overarching objective is to foster an ethical and emotional commitment, both individually and collectively, towards cultivating sustainable habits and coexistence with nature. More specifically, students will identify strategies to combat climate change by examining local issues and advocating for the ethical responsibility to safeguard nature. They will actively participate in initiatives aimed at reaching sustainable development goals through both individual and collective efforts. Furthermore, students will cultivate attitudes and values centred on respect, care, and preservation of individuals, animals, and the environment. This will involve taking individual actions at the local level, such as promoting responsible consumption and supporting local products, practicing sustainable water and energy usage, adopting eco-friendly transportation methods, and implementing effective waste management practices.

In Physical Education [8], students across all grades are taught how to engage with and use the natural environment for recreational activities, emphasising a respectful and responsible approach to contribute to nature conservation. For older students in 5th and 6th grades, there is an additional focus on planning various physical activities in ways that minimise environmental impact and avoid harm to nature.

In the three language areas —native languages (Aranese, Catalan, and Spanish), foreign language, and second foreign language [9–11]— students from 3rd to 6th year develop the ability to communicate the outcomes of research projects covering topics related to the sustainable development goals. They also gain proficiency in implementing sustainable practices when using digital technologies and learn to engage in discussions concerning significant human issues, such as the sustainability of our planet. Additionally, 5th and 6th year students are tasked with recognising, comprehending, and appreciating the linguistic and cultural diversity of countries where the foreign language is spoken, thereby identifying fundamental cultural and linguistic aspects that foster sustainability and a culture of peace.

Sustainability is also integrated into the Mathematics area [12] through problem-solving contexts that encourage students to reflect on environmental challenges and issues related to responsible consumption in real-world scenarios. This approach encourages students to actively engage with these issues and fosters critical reflection on the suitability of proposed solutions within different contexts.

Finally, although the Arts Education curriculum [13] mentions that “[Arts Education is] a powerful tool of social change that promotes awareness and offers opportunities to face current ecosocial problems, from the perspective of sustainability and overcoming ethnocentric views”, nothing specific is mentioned on how sustainability is included within the learning process.

In conclusion, primary school education places a strong emphasis on fostering a deep awareness and understanding of sustainability and respectful practices towards the environment among students, encouraging them to actively seek solutions in response to the pressing challenges posed by the climate crisis.

3.2 Accessibility within the primary school curriculum

In contrast to the comprehensive attention given to sustainability across all the knowledge areas within the primary school curricula, the concept of “accessibility” remains notably absent. Similarly, terms like “disability” or “different abilities” are also not explicitly addressed in the curriculum content.

While diversity is acknowledged across all knowledge areas, the focus primarily revolves around linguistic and cultural aspects in the different language areas; and gender, culture, ethnic, and language diversity in the area of Knowledge of the Natural, Social, and Cultural Environment [6]. Arts Education [13] touches on cultural diversity as well, while Civic Values and Ethics Education [7] addresses ethnic and cultural diversity and minorities. Mathematics [12] also makes a point of highlighting gender diversity within the classroom and in society.

Physical Education [8] appears less defined in its approach to diversity, mentioning the cultivation of attitudes of respect towards “all types of diversity,” potentially encompassing individuals with disabilities, such as those with reduced mobility, although this is not explicitly outlined.

In conclusion, the current primary school curriculum falls short in addressing topics related to accessibility services and measures beneficial for individuals with different abilities. There is a missed opportunity to introduce students to diverse realities and foster understanding and inclusivity towards individuals with disabilities.

3.3 The CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology

The CROMA-GreenSCENT is a pilot methodology organised between the CROMA initiative and the GreenSCENT project seeking to make environmental education accessible to everyone by including aspects of accessibility and sustainability in educational curricula [14]. The CROMA program [15], operated by Fundació Autònoma Solidària, is designed for primary school students aged 10 to 12 who face educational and socio-economic disadvantages. This initiative aims to enhance students' interest in learning by offering interactive workshops facilitated by students from the Autonomous University of Barcelona.

The GreenSCENT project¹ is a three-year European initiative focused on using digital tools to improve accessible environmental education for students across various educational levels, from primary schools to universities.

After reviewing the new curriculum, the CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology was developed to address identified gaps. Firstly, the curriculum overlooks the concepts of accessibility and disability, omitting any introduction to available accessibility services, such as audio description or subtitles. Additionally, while sustainability is integrated across the curriculum areas, the Arts Education curriculum lacks specific details on how sustainability will be incorporated within this area. However, one key aspect of Arts Education involves teaching students to create audiovisual content using various digital tools. This serves as a focal point where the CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology steps in to bridge the gap by integrating sustainability and accessibility concepts together with digital tools.

In the CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology, students actively participate in producing 360-degree videos focused on the sustainability of their school, with a deliberate emphasis on ensuring accessibility for diverse users. Students gain firsthand insights into the experiences of individuals with blindness, low vision, deafness, or hard of hearing through videos created by users with these specific profiles. These videos not only raise awareness but also serve as an initial introduction for students to the different accessibility services required to fully engage with the content.

The students are also provided with a deeper understanding of the reality of people with disabilities through the use of blind and deafness simulators. These simulators enable students to observe the diverse spectrum of experiences within each disability, highlighting the variability and individuality among individuals with visual and hearing impairments. This hands-on experience serves to challenge and dispel typical preconceived notions and stereotypes associated with disabilities, fostering a more nuanced and empathetic perspective among the students.

Finally, students learn the basics of audio description and apply them by creating audio descriptions of the spaces featured in their recordings to enhance accessibility for users with blindness or low vision. Additionally, they learn to introduce themselves in Catalan Sign Language, and how to greet and thank viewers for watching their video.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, while sustainability is deeply embedded across all curriculum areas, the concept of accessibility remains notably absent. The curriculum focuses on fostering respect and understanding for various forms of diversity, including linguistic, cultural, ethnic, and gender diversity, but learning about and understanding disabilities and individuals with different abilities is not mentioned.

The CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology aims to bridge this gap by integrating sustainability and accessibility. Through this workshop, students actively engage in creating a 360-degree immersive video about their school's sustainability, incorporating different accessibility features to cater to diverse users. This hands-on approach provides students with practical insights into accessibility, fostering awareness of the diverse needs within the disability community.

Ultimately, the CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology offers students a meaningful educational experience that goes beyond theoretical concepts, empowering them to embrace inclusivity and understand the varied needs and perspectives of individuals with disabilities in the green transition.

¹ <https://www.green-scent.eu/>

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REFERENCES

- [1] Council of the European Union. Council Resolution on a strategic framework for European cooperation in education and training towards the European Education Area and beyond (2021-2030) 2021/C 66/01. European Union; 2021. Available from: [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32021G0226\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32021G0226(01))
- [2] Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional. Real Decreto 157/2022, de 1 de marzo, por el que se establecen la ordenación y las enseñanzas mínimas de la Educación Primaria. Gobierno de España; 2022. Available from: <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2022/03/01/157/con>
- [3] Departament d'Educació. DECRET 175/2022, de 27 de setembre, d'ordenació dels ensenyaments de l'educació bàsica. Generalitat de Catalunya; 2022. Available from: <https://portaljuridic.gencat.cat/eli/es-ct/d/2022/09/27/175>
- [4] Departament d'Educació. "Disposicions". In: DECRET 175/2022, de 27 de setembre, d'ordenació dels ensenyaments de l'educació bàsica. 2022. p. 30–31.
- [5] Departament d'Educació. "Capítol 2. Currículum". In: DECRET 175/2022, de 27 de setembre, d'ordenació dels ensenyaments de l'educació bàsica. 2022. p. 10.
- [6] Departament d'Educació. "Annex 2. Coneixement del Medi Natural, Social i Cultural". In: DECRET 175/2022, de 27 de setembre, d'ordenació dels ensenyaments de l'educació bàsica. 2022. p. 102–24.
- [7] Departament d'Educació. "Annex 2. Educació en Valors Cívics i Ètics". In: DECRET 175/2022, de 27 de setembre, d'ordenació dels ensenyaments de l'educació bàsica. 2022. p. 142–50.
- [8] Departament d'Educació. "Annex 2. Educació Física". In: DECRET 175/2022, de 27 de setembre, d'ordenació dels ensenyaments de l'educació bàsica. 2022. p. 151–72.
- [9] Departament d'Educació. "Annex 2. Llengua Estrangera". In: DECRET 175/2022, de 27 de setembre, d'ordenació dels ensenyaments de l'educació bàsica. 2022. p. 215–31.
- [10] Departament d'Educació. "Annex 2. Segona Llengua Estrangera". In: DECRET 175/2022, de 27 de setembre, d'ordenació dels ensenyaments de l'educació bàsica. 2022. p. 232–43.
- [11] Departament d'Educació. "Annex 2. Aranès i Literatura a l'Aran, Llengua Castellana i Literatura, Llengua Catalana i Literatura". In: DECRET 175/2022, de 27 de setembre, d'ordenació dels ensenyaments de l'educació bàsica. 2022. p. 197–214.
- [12] Departament d'Educació. "Annex 2. Matemàtiques". In: DECRET 175/2022, de 27 de setembre, d'ordenació dels ensenyaments de l'educació bàsica. 2022. p. 173–93.
- [13] Departament d'Educació. "Annex 2. Educació Artística". In: DECRET 175/2022, de 27 de setembre, d'ordenació dels ensenyaments de l'educació bàsica. 2022. p. 125–41.
- [14] C. Gunella, S. McDonagh, and M. Pujadas Farreras. "Learning accessibility and sustainability through immersive educational experiences: the CROMA-GreenSCENT methodology," ICERI2024 Proceedings, 2024.
- [15] Fundació Autònoma Solidària. CROMA 2.0 - primary school. [cited 2024 Sep 4]. Available from: <https://www.uab.cat/web/volunteering/socio-educational-programs/croma-2-0-primary-school-1345819590272.html>